

CAPACITY BUILDING PROGRAM:

LOCAL AUTHORITIES NEEDS FOR POSITIVE AND CLEAN ENERGY DISTRICTS AND CLIMATE NEUTRALITY

Cities are the place where the European and National climate commitments are put into action.

Across different plans and timelines, all NEUTRALPATH cities have set ambitious goals to achieve climate neutrality and provide a more sustainable future for their citizens.

At the local level, Positive and Clean Energy Districts (PCEDs) can play a key role in the energy transition and contributing to the achievement of the zero emissions targets.

The Capacity Building Program supports the upskilling of public authorities and local communities to enable a successful PCED implementation and unlock the systemic necessary transformation to achieve climate neutrality, focusing on 4 key cross-cutting areas: Governance, Financing, Technology, Social Innovation, and 3 key target sectors: Built Environment, Energy, Mobility.

The following needs and barriers have been retrieved through the Needs Assessment process developed by Eurocities with the 5 city administrations participating in the NEUTRALPATH project: Zaragoza, Dresden, Istanbul, Ghent and Vantaa.

CITIES BARRIERS AND NEEDS ON GOVERNANCE AND POLICY

BARRIERS:

WITHIN THE MUNICIPALITY...

- Working in organizational silos
- Resources and staff skills

...WITH THE LOCAL ECOSYSTEM...

- Difficulty in establishing Public-private partnerships
- Multistakeholder engagement

... WITH OTHER LEVELS OF GOVERNMENT - MULTI-LEVEL GOVERNANCE

- Limiting/conflicting policies among levels of governments (national/regional/local)
- Regulatory barriers
- Rigid Fiscal regulations and public procurement

NEEDS:

- Upskilling and reskilling of public administration
- Enhance cross-departmental coordination and data access/sharing
- Establish cross-sectoral dialogue and long-term collaboration
- Embracing innovative governance models
- Establish long-term Private-public partnerships
- Enhance local/regional/national/EU policy alignment and coordination

CITIES BARRIERS AND NEEDS ON SOCIAL INNOVATION

BARRIERS:

- Conflicting interests from key industries and stakeholders
- Resistance to behavioral change from individuals
- Lack of awareness of climate change
- Difficulty obtaining acceptance and collaboration from homeowners/tenants and other key stakeholders for the PCED implementation measures.

NEEDS:

- Co-design of climate solutions and develop cross-sectoral commitments
- Foster co-ownership of solutions among stakeholders
- Activating the local ecosystem expertise to contribute to the city decarbonisation goals
- Enhance awareness
- Innovative citizen engagement tools, including ICT, and co-creation methods

CITIES BARRIERS AND NEEDS ON TECHNOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

BARRIERS:

- Access to innovative technological solutions
- Access and use of emissions monitoring, evaluation and reporting tools
- Digitalisation skills and tools
- Address intersectionality of technological measures for PCED: energy, building environment, mobility
- High investment cost
- Get all necessary stakeholders on board with measures (renovation)

NEEDS:

- Digitalisation strategies and tools
- Improve access to technology
- Involve local SMEs to drive innovation
- Holistic planning and sectoral integration
- Secure long-term investment planning
- Address social aspects of implementation
- Address regulatory barriers

CITIES BARRIERS AND NEEDS ON FINANCING AND BUSINESS MODELS

BARRIERS:

- Using Innovative financing tools
- Mixing different sources of public funding
- Designing business models for PCED
- Mobilise private investments
- Investment Planning
- Energy efficiency-related investments

NEEDS:

- Enhance financial knowledge within the local administration
- Explore innovative financing tools beyond public funding
- Address a business model for PCED as a process, not a product
- Address the different – and possibly conflicting – interests among key stakeholders
- Involving and coordinating partners and stakeholders from private sectors

The cross-cutting areas for a successful PCED implementation are the same that are needed to enable the systemic transformation for climate neutrality (Governance, Financing, Social Innovation and Technology)

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2030
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Funded by
the European Union